

MODULE FOR SIMULTANEOUS PROCESSING OF DATA FROM MULTI-CHANNEL SENSORS

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Abstract

This article presents methods of digital systems processing data from various sensors or sources, synchronization system and algorithm based on the program developed for data processing in the system. Methods of high-speed data processing in systems with multi-channel analog and digital sensors are analyzed. In a digital system, it has been investigated whether data from multi-channel sensors can be delayed in time t or cause errors in calculation due to the time taken for measurement. In order to eliminate the errors of data obtained from multi-channel sensors, a method and model of synchronous processing were developed.

Keywords: Synchronous processing, meteorological station, meteorological data, dalnomer, optoelectronic system.

Introduction. Simultaneous data synchronization from multi-channel sensors is an important part of any system. In weather-related systems, time synchronization is essential for the correct interpretation and accurate calculation of changing meteorological data. It is important to use the time-synchronized meteorological data system, especially for the purpose of performing special tasks in the FVV, hydrometeorological center, and ballistic artillery and aviation of the military sector. An object moving in space is affected by changes in meteorological parameters. Among these parameters, the influence of wind direction and speed is significant, it can change its

direction every minute and there are errors in achieving certain goals [1]. In practice, almost no studies have been conducted on the device model based on the method of obtaining data from many sensors and their simultaneous processing based on targeting an object moving in space and predicting the point of arrival after a certain time t [2].

In order to target an object moving in space, in addition to the parameters such as the object's distance s and its speed v , atmospheric effects are also important. This affects the change of the second coordinate of the object under the influence of air temperature T_v , wind speed w_0 and direction a_w , air pressure H_0 .

Picture 1. Synchronous data processing module

In order to ensure continuous synchronous operation of the presented system, the synchronous data processing module receives data from several sensors and synchronously processes the received data for time t , finding the values of s , v , T_v , a_{wy} , w , H_0 from the specified virtual correction table [3] transmits it to the screen and to the drive unit at time t_0 (Fig. 1).

The optoelectronic system performs the task of determining the moving object at time t and its speed v . Dalnomer is a device that measures the distance s to a moving object. In the small weather station, 4 sensors are placed for measuring special parameters, which transmit data to the synchronous data processing unit (MSQI) at time t according to the specified special

parameters atmospheric temperature T_v , wind speed w_0 and direction a_w , atmospheric pressure H_0 . In the MSQI block, values such as $\Delta\tau_y$ - elimination of ballistic deviation of atmospheric temperature, a_{wy} - directional angle of wind direction, Y_{st} - wind speed at standard heights are calculated based on special formulas and tables.

According to the block diagram of simultaneous data processing of multi-channel sensors (optoelectronic system, dalnomer, measuring sensors - measuring wind speed and direction, atmospheric pressure, atmospheric temperature), its functional algorithm is presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Algorithm for simultaneous processing of data from multi-channel sensors

The algorithm starts with a loop, reads the data of the optoelectronic system, dalnomer, small weather station continuously every 5 seconds. The optoelectronic system and dalnomer continuously measure the speed and distance of the object and send it to the server to determine the coordinates of the object. In the prediction coordinate determination block, the data change differences in a small weather station are determined using the formulas and special tables below.

Atmospheric pressure change difference is determined

$$\Delta H = H_0 - 750 \quad (1)$$

Here it is: ΔH – difference in pressure change;
 H_0 – measured air pressure.

Air temperature change is considered:

$$\sigma_0 = T_v + \Delta t_y \quad (2)$$

T_v – measured air temperature;
 Δt_y – value obtained from virtual corrections of air temperature;
 σ_0 – virtual temperature.

Table 1.

Virtual corrections that eliminate the effects of air temperature

T_v	below 0	0-5	10-15	20	25	30	40
Δt_y	0	0,5	1,0	1,5	2,0	3,5	4,5

The temperature difference from the normal temperature is determined:

$$\Delta\sigma_0 = \sigma_0 - 15.9 \tag{3}$$

$\Delta\sigma_0$ - difference of temperature from normal temperature;

σ_0 - virtual temperature.

Δt_0 according to the result, it is entered according to table 2 and the temperature deviation values at the standard heights given for each Δt_y standard heights are found.

Table 2.

The dependence of the average temperature deviation Δt_y on Δt_0

Y_M	Δt_0 grad.														
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	20	30	40	50	
200	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-8	-9	-20	-29	-39	-49	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	20	30	-	-	
400	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-6	-7	-8	-9	-19	-29	-38	-48	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	20	30	-	-	
800	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-6	-7	-7	-8	-18	-28	-37	-46	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	20	30	-	-	

here, Δt_y -values of temperature deviation at standard heights.

To calculate the correction for the direction of the blowing wind, the directions of the wind at standard heights are determined.

When we get the wind direction from the weather station in degree values, we convert it to the direction angle and measure the wind direction in the direction angle.

Wind directions at standard altitudes

Y_M	$\Delta\alpha_{wy}$
200	1-00
400	2-00
800	3-00

Wind directions at standard altitudes are determined by adding the measured wind direction to the values given for standard heights.

$$\alpha_{wy} = \alpha_{wo} + \Delta\alpha_{wy}$$

$\Delta\alpha_{wy}$ - correction for wind direction deviation at standard altitudes;

α_{wy} - wind direction at standard altitudes.

The shooting angle is determined by these formulas. The result is sent to the screen and the drive unit.

Summary. The given model is designed to measure the changing parameters of the atmosphere, to target an object moving in space, and to process data from multi-channel sensors to perform special tasks, to transmit the data obtained from them at time t, to predict the point of the object's arrival trajectory, and to determine the launch angle. The model works in real (online) mode. The time t required for simultaneous processing of data and measurement of meteoroparameters is taken into account.

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ENERGY HARVESTING AND RECHARGING FOR WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS

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Abstract

Minimizing energy consumption for wireless sensor networks lifetime is one of the main problems in wireless sensor networks. The problem is long term autonomous operation of wireless sensor networks. This implies harvesting and recharging the sensor nodes during it is operation by employing the energy harvesting method using the sunlight available. The optimized solar energy harvesting and recharging wireless sensor networks operate for an infinite wireless sensor networks lifetime. The simulation results indicate the highest stability for energy harvesting and recharging the wireless sensor networks that indicates good throughput.

Keywords: wireless sensor network; network lifetime; energy consumption; efficiency energy; energy harvesting.

1. Introduction

The generation of wireless technology is rapidly growing and concurrently demand for power consumption to maintain the network. The wireless sensor network (WSNs) is a self-organizing network and communication function. The WSNs has advantages (e.g., avoid wires, flexibility through physical partitions, easily to add new devices, free, accessible through centralized monitor etc.) The various researchers introduced algorithms and different methods which minimize amount of energy required by WSN during the network communication [1], [2]. Low latency, overcomes the limited factors of each and every sensor node in WSNs. Among suggestive algorithm are Power Efficient Gathering in Sensor Information System (PEGASIS), and energy efficiency using the genetic algorithms suggested [3], [4]. Furthermore, given scarcity of the research onto determinants of implementation in energy harvester and recharging literature [5], [6].

The main contributions of this article are energy harvesting from the available sunlight, recharging the sensor nodes and sensor nodes energy consumption

2. Related Works

The principal indication behind charging batteries for WSN based on energy harvesting technology is to Minimize and eliminate the need for maintaining lifetime for the sensor node. Thus, a common selling argument for energy harvesting is extended lifetime compared to batteries that in turn can enable otherwise, unsustainable network solutions. Recently, simultaneous wireless information and energy harvesting has increased its popularity in modern wireless net-

works. Energy harvesting has attracted a lot of attention, since it can prolong the lifetime of WSN under energy constraints [7]. Energy harvesting refers to a process by which energy is derived from the surrounding environment (e.g., wind, wave, vibration, solar, and thermal energy), captured, and stored for later use [8].

3. System model for energy harvesting using sunlight

A sensor node with an energy harvester and a small battery for temporary storage can operate indefinitely, in theory, by perpetually replenishing its battery using the harvested energy. The energy available to these nodes is intermittent and varying; making power management, i.e., transmit power and energy storage control, a crucial matter for efficient operation.

For energy harvesting nodes, an energy storage device is desirable to provide such a power policy. In practice, however, this storage device would have storage losses, leakage, and capacity fading. These in turn can affect the optimum transmission policy. The information transmission from the source node to the destination node is assumed to occur via several clusters of decode and forward relay nodes. The source and relay nodes have the ability to harvest energy from the environment and use that harvested energy to transmit and forward the information to the next hop. Under such an assumption, the objective is to improve energy optimization over a number of transmission frames subject to constraints on energy causality, battery overflow, and time duration for energy harvesting.